

Climatic Compatibility of Building Forms as Solar Receivers across Latitudes

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Note 2: *This paper is the second in a series on the solar performance of building forms. In the present text, "Paper 1" refers to "A latitudinal study of insolation on geometric forms" (submitted to Solar Energy, May 2026); "Paper 3" refers to "Solar Profile Ratio of Building Forms: A Latitude-Dependent Geometric Index" (Zenodo preprint, May 2026, DOI 10.5281/zenodo.20261773). The present paper can be read independently; references to Papers 1 and 3 indicate shared datasets and methodology described therein.*

Abstract

The Form Insolation Index (m-index) established in a companion paper [Paper 1] quantifies the fraction of solar radiation received by a building envelope relative to a horizontal surface, and demonstrates a strong linear relationship with the base-to-surface ratio B/F governed by a latitude-dependent slope coefficient u . The present paper introduces a complementary metric: the Climatic Compatibility index (CC), defined as the Pearson correlation coefficient between the monthly temperature signal D and the monthly m-index m of each form across the 12 months of the year.

A climatically compatible form receives more solar radiation when ambient temperatures are lower, and less when temperatures are higher – the desirable behaviour for a passive solar receiver across all climate types. CC was computed for 92 building form variants across the same 9 locations spanning 6.5°N (Lagos) to 64.1°N (Reykjavik).

CC values range from +0.607 to -0.903, covering nearly the full theoretical range. A clear latitudinal pattern emerges, with the index losing physical meaning in isothermal tropical climates (Lagos, Dakar) and providing maximum discrimination at mid-latitudes (Riyadh, Bologna). Forms with consistently poor CC across all locations share a high B/F ratio and near-horizontal dominant surfaces, which peak in solar collection during summer. The best-performing forms are elongated boxes with the long axis oriented

34 E–W, combining large south-facing vertical surfaces with a pronounced seasonal insolation swing.
35 Together, the m-index and the CC index provide a two-dimensional geometric characterisation of a
36 building form’s solar behaviour: quantity and timing.

37 **Keywords:** Climatic Compatibility, form insolation index, building geometry, solar receivers, seasonal
38 insolation, Pearson correlation, passive solar design, latitudinal study

39 1 Introduction

40 The solar radiation incident on a building envelope is a primary determinant of its thermal behaviour
41 and energy demand for heating and cooling. At the early design stage, when fundamental form
42 decisions are made, detailed simulation is not yet practicable. A simple, physically grounded parameter
43 relating building geometry to radiation availability is therefore of practical value to the designer.

44 The m-index, first introduced by the present author [Author 1999, revalidated 2020], provides such a
45 measure: defined as the ratio of mean irradiation on the envelope to irradiation on a horizontal surface,
46 it is dimensionless, scale-independent, and depends only on form geometry and location. A companion
47 paper [Paper 1] extends this framework to 92 building form variants across 9 locations from Lagos
48 (6.5°N) to Reykjavik (64.1°N) using PVGIS v5.3 satellite data, confirming the linear relationship $m =$
49 $u \cdot (B/F - 1) + 1$ with a location-dependent slope u and a validation mean absolute error of 3.5 percentage
50 points across 22 additional locations.

51 That paper also notes, in its conclusions, that the monthly resolution of the dataset reveals
52 characteristic seasonal signatures by form type and orientation, and that these profiles carry direct
53 implications for the climatic suitability of different building forms – to be examined in the present
54 companion work.

55 The seasonal profile of the m-index is U-shaped for all forms in the northern hemisphere: envelope
56 irradiation is higher in winter (when the low sun favours vertical and inclined surfaces) and lower in
57 summer (when the high sun predominantly strikes horizontal surfaces). A building form that exploits this
58 natural behaviour – receiving more solar energy when the climate is cold and less when it is warm – is
59 inherently well matched to its climate as a passive solar receiver, without any reliance on active
60 systems, shading devices, or thermal mass. The present paper formalises this intuition with a single
61 quantitative index.

62 The concept of matching building form to climate seasonally has a long qualitative tradition in
63 bioclimatic architecture. Olgyay [1963] articulated the principle that building form, orientation, and
64 solar control should respond to the specific climatic demands of a location, identifying temperature and
65 solar radiation as the primary variables to be balanced across seasons. Givoni [1969, 1998] extended this
66 framework to building climatology, establishing the physical basis for passive solar design across

67 different climate types. These foundational works, however, addressed form–climate compatibility in
68 qualitative or element-specific terms – glazing ratios, shading devices, orientation rules of thumb –
69 rather than providing a quantitative geometric index applicable to the full envelope across a systematic
70 range of form types and latitudes.

71 The present study addresses this gap by introducing the “Climatic Compatibility” index [CC] of a form,
72 correlating its average insolation with the ambient temperature during the year. The CC index is
73 computed for 92 forms at 9 locations, and used to rank forms by the degree to which their seasonal
74 insolation profile opposes the seasonal temperature profile of each location. The CC index is directly
75 derived from the m-index of Paper 1, extending its design utility from a single annual value to a
76 seasonally resolved compatibility measure. Together, the m-index (quantity of solar reception) and the
77 CC index (timing of solar reception) constitute a two-dimensional geometric characterisation of a
78 building form’s solar behaviour.

79 The CC index is purely geometric and climatic: it makes no assumptions about building systems, glazing,
80 occupancy, or thermal mass. It represents the optimal passive solar starting condition – the geometric
81 prerequisite for solar compatibility – before any design or engineering intervention.

82 **2 Background**

83 The relationship between building form and solar radiation has been approached from several
84 directions. At the conceptual level, Olgyay [1963] established the foundational principle of bioclimatic
85 design: that building form should respond to the specific climatic demands of its location, balancing
86 solar gain, ventilation, and shading across seasons. His ‘heliothermic’ planning approach identified
87 latitude-dependent optimal orientations and form proportions, but did not quantify the relationship
88 between form geometry and envelope-integrated solar reception.

89 Givoni [1969] provided a more physically rigorous treatment in ‘Man, Climate and Architecture’,
90 establishing the thermophysical basis for passive solar design and the role of building form in
91 moderating internal thermal conditions. His subsequent ‘Climate Considerations in Building and Urban
92 Design’ [1998] extended this framework to a range of climate types, reinforcing the principle that form–
93 climate matching is location-specific and season-dependent.

94 More recent parametric studies have examined specific geometric metrics in relation to solar
95 irradiation. Hachem, Athienitis and Fazio [2011] studied seven housing plan geometries and their effect
96 on solar radiation on equatorial-facing facades, using aspect ratio and surface-to-volume ratio (S/V) as
97 descriptors. Caruso, Fantozzi and Leccese [2013] applied calculus of variations to derive theoretically
98 optimal building forms minimising direct solar irradiation. Mohajeri et al. [2016] analysed compactness
99 indicators for over 10,000 buildings in Geneva, relating urban density and form to annual envelope

100 irradiation. These studies confirm the general principle that geometric exposure governs envelope
101 irradiation, but employ size-dependent metrics (S/V , compactness) unsuitable as pure descriptors of
102 form independent of scale.

103 The base-to-surface ratio B/F , introduced by the present author [Author 1998, 1999], avoids this
104 problem: it is dimensionless, scale-independent, and captures the geometric relationship between the
105 horizontal footprint and the total exposed envelope area. A linear correlation between B/F and the m -
106 index was first established across 71 convex form variants at three locations [Author 1999],
107 subsequently revalidated [Author 2020], and extended to a full latitudinal study in the companion paper
108 [Paper 1].

109 The seasonal dimension of form–climate matching – the question of whether a form’s insolation profile
110 is well-timed relative to the thermal demands of its climate – has not previously been quantified across
111 a systematic form set. The Climatic Compatibility index introduced here fills this gap.

112 **3 Methodology**

113 *3.1 The temperature signal [D]*

114 The monthly temperature signal is defined as:

$$115 \quad D_m = (T_m / \bar{T}_{\text{annual}}) \times 100$$

116 where T_m is the monthly mean temperature and \bar{T}_{annual} is the annual mean temperature of the location.
117 D is dimensionless and purely climatic – no comfort threshold or degree-day base temperature is
118 assumed. Values below 100 indicate months cooler than the annual mean; values above 100 indicate
119 months warmer than the annual mean. One $[D]$ curve is computed per location and is common to all
120 forms at that location. Monthly mean temperatures are sourced from NASA POWER for all 9 study
121 locations.

122 *3.2 The insolation signal [m]*

123 The monthly insolation signal is the monthly m -index of each form, as computed in Paper 1 [4] from the
124 PVGIS v5.3 dataset. It is the ratio of average irradiation on the form surface to that on horizontal. m -
125 index is unitless and no further normalisation is applied: as shown in Section 3.3, the Pearson correlation
126 is invariant to linear scaling of either input, so normalisation by any fixed scalar (such as the monthly
127 maximum across all forms) does not affect the CC value. The raw monthly m -index is therefore used
128 directly.

129 *3.3 The Climatic Compatibility index (CC)*

130 The Climatic Compatibility index of a form at a location is the Pearson correlation coefficient between
131 the monthly temperature signal D and the form's monthly insolation index m across the 12 months of
132 the year:

$$133 \quad \text{CC} = r(D, m) = \text{CORREL}(D, m)$$

134 A value of $\text{CC} = -1$ indicates perfect inverse co-variation: m is highest when D is lowest and vice versa –
135 the ideal Climatic Compatibility. $\text{CC} = +1$ means the insolation signal tracks the temperature signal – the
136 worst compatibility. $\text{CC} = 0$ indicates no seasonal relationship between insolation and temperature.

137 Within any given location, the most negative CC value identifies the most climatically compatible form.

138 The concept expresses the idea of balancing low ambient temperatures with increased insolation and
139 vice versa. A building form well-matched for a location should receive more solar radiation when
140 ambient temperatures are lower, and less when ambient temperatures are higher. The Pearson
141 correlation captures this pattern relationship independently of absolute magnitude or scale – it
142 responds to the seasonal shape of both curves, not their values.

143 The CC index is a derivative of the m -index of Paper 1. The m -index quantifies the total solar reception
144 of a form that varies monthly; CC quantifies the seasonal timing of that reception. A complete
145 characterisation of a form's solar behaviour requires both: a high m -index form with poor CC collects
146 heavily but at the wrong time of year; a form with excellent CC but low m -index collects less than others
147 during warm periods. The optimal passive solar form performs well on both measures.

148 *3.4 Data sources and study locations*

149 Monthly m -index values for all 92 form variants at all 9 locations are derived from the PVGIS v5.3
150 dataset as established in Paper 1. The study spans 6.5°N (Lagos) to 64.1°N (Reykjavik) across five Köppen
151 climate zones. Köppen classifications are taken from the Beck et al. [2023] global raster dataset at 0.1°
152 resolution.

153

155 Table 1: Study locations, Köppen classification and annual mean temperature.

Location	Code	Lat.	Köppen	Ann. T (°C)	Description
Lagos	LAG	6.5°N	Aw	26.7	Tropical savanna
Dakar	DAK	14.7°N	BSh	24.2	Hot semi-arid
Riyadh	RIY	24.7°N	BWh	26.9	Hot desert
Alexandria	ALE	31.2°N	BWh	21.2	Hot semi-arid
Athens	ATH	38.0°N	Csa	18.4	Hot-summer Mediterranean
Bologna	BOL	44.5°N	Cfa	14.0	Humid subtropical
London	LON	51.5°N	Cfb	11.1	Temperate oceanic
Aarhus	AAR	56.2°N	Cfb	9.4	Temperate oceanic
Reykjavik	REY	64.1°N	Cfc	4.0	Subpolar oceanic

156 *3.5 Building forms*

157 The 92 form variants are identical to those of Paper 1, comprising seven families: rectilinear boxes,
 158 pitched roofs, rectangular pyramids, cones, cylinders, barrel vaults, and a hemisphere. Each family is
 159 parametrised by height/width ratio (h/w) and, where applicable, length/width ratio (l/w) and
 160 orientation. The orientation conventions are summarised in Table A of Paper 1 and reproduced here for
 161 reference:

163
164

Figure 2: The box family "B" with 40 variations of Width/Height and Width/Length ratios. All cases are shown having equal volume equal to a unit cube

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Figure 3: The pitched roof family "R" with 30 variations

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Figure 4: The pyramid "P", cone "K", cylinder "C", vault "V", and hemisphere geometric families with 22 variations in total.

Table A: Form orientation conventions (after Table A of Paper 1).

Form	Code	Orientation	Long axis	Facing	Proportions
Box	B	or=0°	N–S	Long walls E/W	h/w: 0.25, 0.5, 1, 2, 4 / l/w: 1, 2, 4
		or=45°	SW–NE	Long walls SE/NW	
		or=90°	E–W	Long walls N/S	
Pitched roof	R	or=0° (ridge E–W)		Slopes S/N	h/w: 0.25, 0.5, 1, 2, 4 / l/w: 0.25, 1, 4
		or=90° (ridge N–S)		Slopes E/W	
Vault	V	or=0° (axis N–S)		Curved surface E/W	l/w: 1, 2, 4
		or=90° (axis E–W)		Curved surface N/S	
Pyramid	P	cardinal	–	–	h/w: 0.25, 0.5, 1, 2, 4
Cone	K	–	–	–	h/w: 0.25, 0.5, 1, 2, 4
Cylinder	C	–	–	–	h/w: 0.25, 0.5, 1, 2, 4
Hemisphere	H	–	–	–	single variant

171 **4 Results**

172 *4.1 Overview of the CC matrix*

173 The Climatic Compatibility index was computed for all 92 form variants across 9 locations spanning
174 6.5°N to 64.1°N. CC values range from +0.607 (form R6 at Lagos) to –0.903 (form B16 at Riyadh),
175 covering nearly the full theoretical range of the index. A clear latitudinal pattern emerges: at tropical
176 locations (Lagos, Dakar) CC values are near zero or positive; at mid-latitude locations (Riyadh through
177 London) CC values are strongly negative; at high latitudes (Aarhus, Reykjavik) the CC range narrows and
178 between-form differences diminish. The full results are presented in Table B (Appendix).

179 *Table B: Three top and bottom form rankings per location. Full list in Table C (Appendix).*

rank	LAG	DAK	RIY	ALE	ATH	BOL	LON	AAR	REY
1	R5	R1	B16	R5	B8	B6	R24	R24	R28
2	R11	R7	B24	B8	B13	B30	R6	R30	R22
3	R9	K1	B32	B24	B16	B38	R18	R22	B11

90	P1	R9	R11	P1	P1	R3	P1	R3	R30

91	K1	R11	P1	R6	R11	P1	R3	K1	R24
92	R6	R5	K1	K1	R5	R5	R5	R5	R18

180 *4.2 Results by location*

181 *4.2.1 Lagos (LAG, 6.5°N, Köppen: Aw)*

182 CC values range from -0.724 to $+0.607$. The near-isothermal annual temperature profile (annual mean
 183 26.7°C , monthly range $25\text{--}28^{\circ}\text{C}$) produces a D signal with negligible seasonal variation. CORREL
 184 therefore reflects statistical noise rather than a meaningful climate–form relationship. Lagos represents
 185 the tropical boundary condition of the index: below approximately 15°N with low seasonal temperature
 186 amplitude, the CC index loses physical significance. Near-zero CC does not imply that all forms are
 187 equally suitable – it means the seasonal temperature signal is too weak to differentiate between forms
 188 through this index; form choice at such locations must be guided by other criteria. Several high B/F roof
 189 forms (R6: $+0.607$, V5: $+0.543$, P5: $+0.522$) produce positive CC – their insolation profiles happen to
 190 follow the weak temperature curve rather than oppose it.

191

192 *Figure 5: Monthly temperature signal D (T%, dotted) and monthly m-index profiles for B33 (B/F=0.59), H1*
 193 *(B/F=0.50), and P1 (B/F=0.894) at Lagos (LAG), Athens (ATH), and Reykjavik (REY). The three locations*
 194 *illustrate the tropical boundary condition (near-flat D at LAG), maximum seasonal opposition (ATH), and*
 195 *the high-latitude regime where sub-zero winter temperatures drive D below zero (REY).*

196 *4.2.2 Dakar (DAK, 14.7°N, Köppen: BSh)*

197 CC values range from -0.395 to $+0.379$. The seasonal temperature signal is marginally stronger than at
 198 Lagos but remains weak. Dakar represents a transitional regime where the index begins to differentiate
 199 between forms. R4 ($+0.379$), R10 (0.000) and R12 ($+0.242$) show positive or near-zero values – these

200 pitched roof forms with low pitch and east–west slope orientation collect more solar radiation in the
201 brief warm season, reinforcing rather than opposing the temperature curve.

202 4.2.3 *Riyadh (RIY, 24.7°N, Köppen: BWh)*

203 CC values range from –0.697 to –0.903, a spread of 0.206 – one of the widest in the study. Despite its
204 southerly latitude, the hot desert climate generates a strong seasonal temperature signal driven by the
205 large annual temperature swing (15.7°C to 38°C). Tall elongated box forms with the long axis oriented E–
206 W (or=90°, large walls facing N/S) achieve the best compatibility (forms B8, B16, B24, B32, B40 sharing
207 the top ranks), while wide low-pitched roof forms (K1: rank 92, R11: rank 90, R5: rank 82) rank last.

208 4.2.4 *Alexandria (ALE, 31.2°N, Köppen: BWh)*

209 CC values range from –0.686 to –0.763, a spread of 0.077 – the narrowest among valid locations.
210 Alexandria shares the BWh classification with Riyadh, but the Mediterranean coastal influence
211 moderates the seasonal temperature amplitude, reducing the CC index’s discriminating power. Form
212 rankings are broadly consistent with Riyadh: elongated boxes at or=90° lead, high B/F roofs and
213 pyramids trail. The similar Köppen code but different CC spread between Riyadh and Alexandria
214 illustrates that Köppen classification alone does not fully predict the discriminating power of the CC
215 index – the amplitude of the seasonal temperature signal within a climate zone is the determining
216 factor.

217 4.2.5 *Athens (ATH, 38.0°N, Köppen: Csa)*

218 CC values range from –0.730 to –0.834, a spread of 0.104. The classic Mediterranean regime – cold
219 winters, hot summers – produces strong seasonal opposition between D and m. Elongated box forms at
220 or=0° dominate the top ranks, with B8, B13 and B16 occupying positions 1–3.; K1, P1, R9 and R11
221 occupy the bottom.

222 4.2.6 *Bologna (BOL, 44.5°N, Köppen: Cfa)*

223 CC values range from –0.655 to –0.859, a spread of 0.204 – the widest in the study, matching Riyadh.
224 The humid continental climate produces the strongest seasonal signal in the dataset. Elongated boxes at
225 or=0° (long axis N–S, large walls facing E/W; forms B6, B14, B22, B30, B38) lead the rankings – a notable
226 contrast to the or=90° dominance at more southerly locations. This latitude-dependent orientation shift
227 within the box form group is discussed further in Section 4.4.

228 4.2.7 *London (LON, 51.5°N, Köppen: Cfb)*

229 CC values range from –0.660 to –0.814, a spread of 0.154. The temperate oceanic climate allows clear
230 differentiation between forms. R24 achieves the best CC at London (rank 1) – a steep pitched roof
231 (h/w=2, l/w=4, or=90°: ridge N–S, slopes facing E and W). R5 and K1 remain consistently worst. Box

232 forms cluster narrowly around -0.763 , with CC differences between orientation variants of less than
233 0.015 – orientation choice has limited impact on Climatic Compatibility for box forms at this latitude.

234 4.2.8 Aarhus (AAR, 56.2°N , Köppen: Cfb)

235 CC values range from -0.570 to -0.696 , a spread of 0.126 . The temperate oceanic climate at this latitude
236 shows increasing heating dominance. R24 and R30 lead the rankings – steep pitched roofs with ridge N–
237 S (east–west slopes) performing consistently well at high latitudes. P1 and K1 remain worst.

238 4.2.9 Reykjavik (REY, 64.1°N , Köppen: Cfc)

239 CC values range from -0.571 to -0.696 , a spread of 0.125 . The subpolar oceanic regime is heating-
240 dominated throughout the year. Notable rank inversions appear relative to mid-latitude locations: R18
241 (pitched roof, $h/w=1$, $l/w=4$, $or=90^{\circ}$ – ridge N–S, slopes facing E and W) drops to rank 92 – worst of all
242 forms at this location. Its east–west slopes receive high irradiation in summer, when the low Reykjavik
243 sun spends many hours in the eastern and western sky, and very low irradiation in the near-dark winter
244 months – placing its m curve in phase with D rather than in opposition. By contrast, R28 (pitched roof,
245 $h/w=4$, $l/w=4$, $or=90^{\circ}$ – same ridge orientation but very steep slopes) rises to rank 1: the extreme pitch
246 reduces summer collection on the near-vertical east–west faces while providing a more stable annual
247 profile, yielding better seasonal opposition.

248 4.3 Consistent performers across locations

249 Table C reveals two asymmetric patterns of rank consistency across the 9 study locations.

250 The worst performers are universal. Five forms appear in the bottom ranks at every location without
251 exception: K1 (Cone $h/w=0.25$, $B/F=0.894$), P1 (Pyramid $h/w=0.25$, $B/F=0.894$), R5 (Pitched $h/w=0.25$,
252 $l/w=4$, $or=0^{\circ}$, $B/F=0.847$), R9 (Pitched $h/w=0.5$, $l/w=1$, $or=0^{\circ}$, $B/F=0.522$), and R11 (Pitched $h/w=0.5$,
253 $l/w=4$, $or=0^{\circ}$, $B/F=0.65$). Their global ranks in Table C are 92, 87, 86, 79 and 90 respectively. All share a
254 high B/F ratio and near-horizontal dominant surfaces whose insolation peaks in summer, directly
255 opposing the desired seasonal behaviour. This universality holds regardless of climate type or latitude: a
256 form with these geometric characteristics is climatically incompatible as a passive solar receiver across
257 the full range studied.

258 No equivalent universal best list exists. The best-performing form type shifts with latitude, as the
259 location columns of Table C show: elongated box forms at $or=90^{\circ}$ (long axis E–W, large south-facing
260 walls) occupy ranks 1–3 at Riyadh, Alexandria and Athens — B8, B16 and B24 consistently — while steep
261 pitched roofs with N–S ridge (east–west slopes) emerge as the best performers at London, Aarhus and
262 Reykjavik, with R24 and R28 reaching ranks 1–2 at those locations. The global ranking reflects this shift:
263 R28 achieves global rank 10 and R24 rank 13, competitive with the elongated boxes (B8 rank 26, B16
264 rank 25), precisely because their advantage extends across a wider latitudinal range.

265 This asymmetry — universal consensus at the bottom, latitude-dependent variation at the top — is itself
 266 a finding. A short list of geometrically incompatible forms can be identified independently of location.
 267 The positive recommendation, by contrast, requires knowing the latitude: elongated E–W boxes for the
 268 subtropics and Mediterranean zone, steep pitched roofs with east–west slopes for temperate and
 269 subpolar latitudes.

270 *4.4 Orientation effects – elongated forms ($l/w=4$)*

271 Orientation effects are most pronounced in the most elongated variants ($l/w=4$) of each form type,
 272 where one face pair dominates the envelope area. The analysis below focuses on these extreme cases.
 273 Orientation conventions for all form types are given in Table A.

274
 275
 276 *Figure 6: Elongated forms discussed in 4.4*

277 *4.4.1 Box forms ($l/w=4$)*

278 Within every box height group, the three orientation variants produce a consistent CC ranking at all
 279 locations: $or=90^\circ$ outranks $or=0^\circ$, which outranks $or=45^\circ$. The $or=45^\circ$ penalty is physically direct: with the
 280 long axis oriented SW–NE, both large face pairs point toward SE/NW and NE/SW, avoiding south
 281 exposure entirely and eliminating the winter insolation peak that makes $or=90^\circ$ effective. Table C
 282 illustrates this for the $h/w=0.25$ group at Athens: B8 ($or=90^\circ$, long axis E–W) ranks 1st, B6 ($or=0^\circ$, long
 283 axis N–S) ranks 34th, B7 ($or=45^\circ$) ranks 51st. The same order holds across all height groups and all
 284 locations, and is consistent with the worst-case m-index finding of Paper 1 for the same orientation.

285 A latitude-dependent shift is apparent within the $or=0^\circ$ vs $or=90^\circ$ comparison at Bologna ($44.5^\circ N$): the
 286 $or=0^\circ$ variants rank highest at Bologna, whereas $or=90^\circ$ dominates at more southerly locations. This
 287 suggests a crossover latitude for the relative advantage of the two principal orientations, located
 288 somewhere between approximately $38^\circ N$ (Athens) and $44^\circ N$ (Bologna) for box forms.

289 *4.4.2 Pitched roof forms ($l/w=4$)*

290 The orientation effect in pitched roofs cannot be separated from pitch angle:

- 291 • Shallow pitches ($h/w \leq 0.5$; R5/R6, R11/R12): both orientations rank poorly at mid-latitudes
 292 (ranks 82–92). The near-horizontal south-facing slope of $or=0^\circ$ behaves effectively as a flat roof,

293 collecting maximally in summer. The orientation distinction has little practical consequence at
294 shallow pitch.

- 295 • Steep pitches ($h/w \geq 2$; R23/R24, R29/R30): $\text{or}=0^\circ$ (south-facing slope) performs well at mid-
296 latitudes – ranks 6–25 at ALE and ATH. The steep south slope acts analogously to a south-facing
297 vertical wall, favouring winter solar collection. By contrast, $\text{or}=90^\circ$ (east–west slopes) performs
298 better at high latitudes: R24 and R30 reach ranks 1–2 at AAR and LON, where the low summer
299 sun strikes east–west slopes throughout long summer days while winter insolation is limited
300 regardless of orientation.
- 301 • A crossover latitude exists for each pitch angle, below which $\text{or}=0^\circ$ (south slope) outperforms
302 $\text{or}=90^\circ$ and above which the advantage reverses. From the rank matrix, this crossover for steep
303 roofs ($h/w \geq 2$) falls between approximately 44°N (Bologna) and 52°N (London). The crossover is
304 consistent with a shift to lower latitudes as pitch angle increases, though quantification across all
305 pitch angles is beyond the scope of this study.

306 4.4.3 Vault forms ($l/w=4$)

307 V5 ($\text{or}=0^\circ$, curved surface facing E/W) performs well at DAK (rank 7), LON (rank 5) and AAR (rank 11) – a
308 wide spread of latitudes. V6 ($\text{or}=90^\circ$, curved surface facing S/N) ranks better at LAG (rank 14) and ALE
309 (rank 27) but poorly at most other locations (ranks 66–88). The east–west curved vault (V5) thus shows
310 broader Climatic Compatibility than the south-facing vault (V6). This result contrasts with the pitched
311 roof finding for steep pitches, where the south-facing slope is advantageous at mid-latitudes. The
312 difference lies in the curvature: the vault surface distributes insolation across a range of angles rather
313 than concentrating it on a single slope, producing a more diffuse and seasonally stable profile. The east–
314 west curved surface (V5) avoids the summer insolation peak that afflicts the south-facing vault (V6),
315 yielding better seasonal opposition to the temperature curve across most valid locations.

316 5 Discussion

317 5.1 Relationship to the m-index

318 The Form Insolation index [m-index] (Paper 1) and the Climatic Compatibility index [CC] (this paper) are
319 complementary rather than competing descriptors. The m-index answers the question: how much solar
320 radiation does this form receive annually relative to the horizontal? The CC index answers: is that
321 reception well-timed relative to the thermal character of this climate?

322 A form can score well on one measure and poorly on the other. A wide flat roof (high B/F, high m-index
323 at low latitudes) collects substantial radiation but poorly timed – peaking in summer when solar gain is
324 unwanted. An elongated box at $\text{or}=90^\circ$ has lower annual m than a hemisphere of equal B/F, but far
325 better CC at mid-latitudes. The design implication is clear: optimising for m-index alone, without regard

326 to seasonal distribution, is insufficient for passive solar design at mid-latitudes. Both measures are
327 needed (see also Figure 7 for the seasonal m-index profiles across all locations).

328 5.2 Physical interpretation of the CC index

329 The CC index formalises an intuition long present in bioclimatic design literature – that building form
330 should be well-matched to the seasonal demands of its climate – but provides for the first time a
331 quantitative, scale-independent measure applicable to a systematic set of geometric forms across a
332 wide latitudinal range. Its inputs are monthly ambient temperature data and the m-index values of
333 Paper 1 [3]; no parameters such as building system, occupant, or comfort are involved. The U-shaped
334 seasonal profile of the m-index is visible in Figure 7 for all nine locations.

335 The near-universally negative CC values across valid locations confirm that the natural U-shape of the m-
336 index profile (driven by solar geometry) is inherently opposed to the arch-shape of the temperature
337 profile (driven by the seasonal cycle) for all form types in the northern hemisphere. This geometric
338 opposition is not a designed outcome but a consequence of the same physics that makes passive solar
339 design viable: low winter sun angles favour vertical and inclined surfaces at the same time that low
340 temperatures create heating demand.

341 The residual variation within this general opposition – the range of CC values from -0.655 to -0.903
342 across valid locations – reflects the degree to which specific form geometry and orientation amplify or
343 attenuate this natural tendency. Forms that concentrate envelope area on near-horizontal surfaces
344 (high B/F, wide flat bases) lose this seasonal advantage; forms that maximise vertical south-facing area
345 (elongated boxes at $\text{or}=90^\circ$) exploit it most fully.

346
347 *Figure 7: (Left) -- Monthly mean m-index averaged across all 92 form variants, for the nine study locations*
348 *(REY–LAG, 64°N–6.5°N). Values above 100% indicate months in which the area-weighted envelope mean*
349 *irradiation exceeds the horizontal reference G_o . The U-shaped seasonal profile deepens with increasing*
350 *latitude, reflecting the greater seasonal contrast in solar altitude at high latitudes. The local depression at*
351 *Lagos and Dakar in June–July reflects overhead sun passage at equatorial latitudes. The anomalous*
352 *December value at Reykjavik is discussed in the text. The depth of the U-shape reflects the amplitude of*

353 *seasonal solar altitude variation, which increases with latitude. Source: Paper 1 [3].*
354 *(Right) – Monthly ambient temperatures in the nine study locations. The correlation of the two graphs is*
355 *the subject of this work.*

356 *5.3 The tropical boundary condition*

357 At Lagos and Dakar, the CC index loses discriminating power because the seasonal temperature signal D
358 is too weak to define a meaningful cold/warm opposition. This is not a failure of the index but a correct
359 identification of a physical boundary: below approximately 15°N in the study dataset, the seasonal solar
360 geometry no longer aligns with a meaningful thermal demand cycle. Form choice for passive solar
361 purposes at these latitudes must be driven by shading, ventilation and solar control rather than seasonal
362 insolation maximisation – consistent with the established bioclimatic literature for tropical climates
363 [Olgay 1963, Givoni 1998].

364 *5.4 The high-latitude boundary condition*

365 A second boundary condition limits the reliability of the CC index at the upper end of the latitudinal
366 range. At Reykjavik (64.1°N) and, to a lesser degree, Aarhus (56.2°N), the seasonal temperature signal D
367 remains meaningful — the annual temperature amplitude at Reykjavik is sufficient to define a clear
368 cold/warm cycle — but the geometric solar regime that underpins the m-index begins to break down. A
369 companion study Paper 3 [4] documents a progressive decoupling between the Solar Profile Ratio (a
370 radiation-free geometric index of envelope solar exposure) and the m-index above approximately 60°N:
371 the Pearson correlation between the two indices, which exceeds 0.97 from Dakar through Bologna,
372 declines to 0.944 at London and 0.824 at Aarhus, and collapses to -0.169 at Reykjavik. This decoupling
373 has two compounding causes: the geometric effect of the sun in higher latitudes spending an increasing
374 proportion of daylight hours at very low elevations, which reduces the discriminating power of surface
375 orientation, and a rising diffuse fraction K_d , which further weakens the directional solar signal on which
376 vertical surface advantage depends. As a consequence, the seasonal m-index profile at high latitudes no
377 longer reliably reflects the geometric properties of the form, and CC values at Reykjavik and Aarhus
378 carry greater uncertainty than those at mid-latitude locations. The CC index should therefore be
379 understood as fully interpretable across approximately 15°N to 60°N — bounded at the lower end by
380 insufficient seasonal temperature amplitude and at the upper end by the breakdown of the directional
381 solar regime.

382 *5.5 Cross-location rank consistency*

383 The rank of forms by CC is broadly consistent across the seven valid locations (RIY through REY) for the
384 extreme performers: the worst-ranked forms (K1, P1, R5, R9, R11) maintain their position universally,
385 while the best-ranked mid-latitude forms (B8, B16, B24, B32, B40) hold their advantage from Riyadh to

386 Athens. At higher latitudes (LON, AAR, REY), steep pitched roof forms emerge as the best performers,
387 displacing the elongated boxes that dominate at lower latitudes.

388 This partial consistency – universal consensus at the extremes, latitude-dependent variation in the
389 middle of the ranking – is itself a finding: certain geometric configurations are climatically incompatible
390 regardless of location, while the optimal form for a specific climate depends on latitude. This has direct
391 implications for design guidance: a short list of universally poor forms can be identified independently of
392 location, while the positive recommendation requires knowing the latitude range.

393 *5.6 Vernacular parallels*

394 The CC-compatible form types find parallels in vernacular architecture. At mid-latitudes, the best
395 performers are elongated boxes at $\alpha=90^\circ$ — long axis E–W, large walls facing south — the canonical
396 orientation of traditional farmhouses across the Mediterranean and central Europe, adapted over
397 centuries to maximise winter solar penetration on the main south façade. At high latitudes, the best
398 performers are steep pitched roofs with N–S ridge and east–west slopes — consistent with the
399 dominant roof type of northern European vernacular, where the steep pitch serves structural and snow-
400 shedding purposes and the east–west faces receive available low-angle winter radiation across long
401 days. The consistently worst performers — flat-based forms with near-horizontal surfaces — belong to
402 tropical and desert vernacular, where shading from overhead sun is the governing design principle.

403 These parallels suggest that the CC index recovers, in quantitative geometric form, design principles that
404 vernacular builders arrived at empirically over long periods of climate-adapted construction. This is not a
405 validation of the index – vernacular architecture is driven by many factors beyond solar geometry – but
406 it offers a reassuring correspondence between the analytical result and accumulated building wisdom.

407 **6 Conclusions**

408 The Climatic Compatibility index derives from the Pearson correlation coefficient between the monthly
409 temperature signal D (monthly T normalised to annual mean T) and the monthly Form Insolation index
410 m . This metric provides a robust, parameter-free index of Climatic Compatibility for building forms as
411 solar receivers. The index requires no assumptions about building systems, comfort thresholds, or
412 occupant behaviour; its sole inputs are standard climate data and the m -index values established in
413 Paper 1 [3].

414 CC values were computed for 92 building form variants at 9 locations spanning 6.5°N to 64.1°N , leading
415 to the following conclusions, based on the descriptions in section 4.2:

- 416 • The index loses physical significance at tropical locations (Lagos, Dakar) where the seasonal
417 temperature signal is too weak to define a meaningful thermal demand cycle. All other seven
418 locations provide useful distinction between forms.
- 419 • A clear latitudinal gradient in CC range is observed: maximum difference at Riyadh (BWh, spread
420 0.206) and Bologna (Cfa, spread 0.204); minimum at Alexandria (BWh coastal, spread 0.077) and
421 the high-latitude locations (Aarhus, Reykjavik, spread ~0.125).
- 422 • Forms with consistently poor CC across all valid locations share a high B/F ratio and near-
423 horizontal dominant surfaces: K1, P1, R5, R9, R11. These forms peak in solar collection during
424 summer, reinforcing rather than opposing the temperature signal.
- 425 • Forms with consistently best CC at mid-latitudes (Riyadh–Athens) are elongated boxes with long
426 axis E–W (or=90°): B8, B16, B24, B32, B40. Their large south-facing vertical surfaces produce a
427 pronounced winter insolation peak with low summer collection.
- 428 • Orientation effects are systematic for elongated forms. For box forms, or=45° is universally the
429 least compatible orientation. A crossover between or=0° and or=90° occurs between
430 approximately 38°N and 44°N. For steep pitched roofs, the south-facing slope (or=0°) is
431 advantageous at mid-latitudes; east–west slopes (or=90°) perform better at high latitudes, with a
432 crossover between approximately 44°N and 52°N.
- 433 • The CC index complements the m-index of Paper 1 [3]: together they provide a two-dimensional
434 geometric description of a building form’s solar behaviour – quantity (m) and timing (CC).
435 Neither alone is sufficient for passive solar design guidance.
- 436 • The best-performing forms identified by the CC analysis correspond to canonical types in
437 climate-adapted vernacular architecture across the latitudinal range studied, suggesting that the
438 index recovers in quantitative form principles arrived at empirically over long periods of building
439 practice.
- 440 Future work could extend the CC framework in two directions: empirical validation through
441 documented vernacular building stock — testing whether historically climate-adapted building types
442 cluster toward high CC values across different latitudinal zones — and simulation-based
443 quantification of the heating demand reduction achievable by selecting high-CC forms relative to
444 climatically poor alternatives.

445 7 References

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- 468

469 **Appendix: Climatic Compatibility Rankings — Full Results**

470 Table B presents the complete CC ranking matrix for all 92 building form variants across the 9 study
 471 locations, together with the global ranking derived from the sum of location ranks.

472 Columns LAG through REY give the rank of each form by CC value at each location (rank 1 = most
 473 negative CC = best Climatic Compatibility; rank 92 = least compatible). The column headed "sum" is the
 474 arithmetic sum of the nine location ranks for each form. The column headed "global ranking" is the rank
 475 of each form by sum, from 1 (lowest sum = most consistently compatible across all locations) to 92
 476 (highest sum = least compatible).

477 Two notes apply to the interpretation of this table. First, ranks at Lagos (LAG) and Dakar (DAK) carry
 478 reduced physical significance: at these tropical locations the seasonal temperature signal is too weak to
 479 define a meaningful thermal demand cycle, and CC values reflect statistical noise rather than genuine

480 Climatic Compatibility (Sec. 5.3). Their inclusion in the sum is retained for completeness. Second, tied
481 global ranks appear where two forms share an identical rank sum; in such cases the RANK function
482 assigns both forms the same rank and the subsequent rank is skipped.

CLIMATE COMPETENCE per m-index & temperature correlation									
rank per location	LAG	DAK	RIY	ALE	ATH	BOL	LON	AAR	REY
1	R5	R1	B16	R5	B6	B6	R24	R24	R28
2	R11	R7	B24	B8	B13	B30	R6	R30	R22
3	R9	K1	B32	B24	B16	B38	R18	R22	B11
4	R3	R24	B40	B32	B24	B14	R12	R28	B36
5	R7	R18	B8	B40	B29	B22	V5	B22	R4
6	R1	R30	R26	B18	B32	R18	B22	B6	V3
7	R17	V5	R8	R26	B40	B19	B14	B14	B3
8	R15	B30	R14	R29	B5	B35	B30	B30	B19
9	R13	B38	R2	R14	B21	B27	B38	B38	B27
10	P3	B14	R20	B29	B37	B3	B6	B3	R10
11	V2	B22	B5	B37	R2	B11	R22	B11	R13
12	P2	R12	B13	R8	R20	R25	R30	B19	R16
13	V4	B6	B21	B5	R29	R19	V3	B27	R19
14	V6	R6	B37	B13	B1	R30	R18	B36	R26
15	B4	R13	B29	B21	B9	B33	R4	R25	P5
16	B15	R19	R29	R2	B17	B1	R10	P4	V1
17	B28	K2	B9	R20	B25	B25	B3	P5	B1
18	B2	R25	B33	R27	B33	R16	B11	V6	B9
19	B30	B36	B1	R23	R8	B9	B19	R19	B17
20	B34	B27	B17	P5	R14	B17	B27	V3	B25
21	B22	V3	B25	B25	R28	R28	B35	B1	B33
22	B39	B34	R27	B1	R27	R13	R25	B9	R7
23	B10	B11	V1	B9	B19	B5	R19	B17	P4
24	B23	B10	R28	B17	B27	V5	V1	B25	P3
25	B31	B19	P5	B33	B3	B13	R13	B33	B13
26	B38	B31	C1	R21	B11	B37	R28	R13	B21
27	B6	B3	C2	R28	B35	B21	P4	R20	B29
28	B14	B12	C3	V6	R23	R12	B9	R26	B37
29	B20	B23	C4	K5	R25	B29	B17	V1	R20
30	B26	B2	C5	C2	R4	V3	B25	B29	R26
31	R19	B20	R23	R3	R21	R10	B33	B5	B5
32	B36	B15	R10	C3	R22	R27	B1	B13	R8
33	B18	B18	R16	C4	P5	V1	R20	B21	R14
34	K4	B26	K5	C5	B6	B16	R14	B37	R21
35	B7	B28	B7	V1	B14	R14	P5	R16	R27
36	B12	B38	B20	V4	P4	P5	C2	R27	R15
37	B35	B39	B4	B3	V1	B8	B5	B8	P2
38	B3	B7	B28	R18	B22	B32	B13	B16	R2
39	B19	H1	B31	C1	B30	B40	B21	B24	B8
40	B27	B4	B34	B2	R10	B24	B29	B32	B15
41	R21	R22	B39	B10	R19	R21	B37	B40	B24
42	K3	K5	R22	V2	B38	R25	R2	R14	B32
43	R23	K3	B2	B4	R18	R8	R8	R2	B40
44	R25	P1	B10	B11	C1	R2	P3	R4	V2
45	B11	C5	B18	B19	C3	R20	C1	R8	C1
46	B9	R16	B23	B20	C4	R29	C3	R18	C2
47	B5	R28	B26	B26	C5	R22	C4	R21	C3
48	B21	C2	B36	B27	R28	R4	C6	R6	C4
49	B1	C3	B15	B28	C2	P4	R27	R10	C5
50	B25	C4	R4	B31	K5	R23	K5	R23	B14
51	B33	C1	B11	B35	B7	R24	B8	R29	B30
52	B17	K4	B12	B36	K4	C4	R21	R15	R1
53	B32	R10	R21	B39	V3	C1	R26	P3	K4
54	B37	R4	B3	R25	B4	C5	B16	R17	K5
55	B13	B25	B19	B12	B18	R6	B24	R12	B6
56	B16	V1	B27	B15	B23	C3	B32	C1	B22
57	B29	B1	B35	B18	B28	C2	B40	C2	B38
58	B40	V2	K4	B23	B2	P3	K4	C5	R23
59	B24	B9	P4	B34	B10	K5	R29	C3	R29
60	B8	P4	V6	P4	B15	R15	R23	C4	K3
61	R27	B17	V3	B7	B20	K4	R15	K4	R9
62	R25	B33	V4	R10	B25	B12	K3	K5	R17
63	R20	P6	R25	K4	B31	B28	B23	R7	V5
64	K5	P3	V2	R19	B34	B7	B2	V2	H1
65	R29	R3	H1	R22	B35	B23	B4	K3	V4
66	C3	R27	R19	K3	B39	B31	B7	V4	R6
67	R14	R21	B6	H1	B12	B15	B10	V6	B2
68	R28	B5	K3	R4	R24	B26	B12	B7	B4
69	P4	B13	B14	R17	R6	B4	B15	B4	B7
70	C5	B21	B22	B6	V2	B34	B18	B10	B10
71	C2	B29	B30	R15	V4	B18	B20	B12	B12
72	C4	B37	B38	P3	R13	B38	B28	B15	B15
73	P5	R20	R30	V3	V6	B20	B28	B18	B18
74	C1	R14	P3	B22	H1	B39	B31	B20	B20
75	R22	R26	R15	B38	K3	B10	B34	B23	B23
76	R8	R8	R17	B14	V5	R17	B36	B26	B26
77	R30	R2	V5	B30	R15	B2	B39	B26	B28
78	H1	B16	R3	R30	R19	V2	H1	B31	B31
79	R2	B40	R24	R13	R12	K3	R7	B34	B34
80	V1	B24	R18	R7	R17	V4	R17	B36	B36
81	R16	B32	R13	R18	R30	H1	V2	B39	B39
82	R24	R29	R5	V5	P3	V6	V4	H1	K2
83	K2	B8	R12	K2	R1	R7	V6	B2	R11
84	V3	R15	K2	R9	R7	K2	K2	R9	V6
85	R10	V4	R8	R1	K2	P2	P2	P2	P1
86	V5	R23	R7	R12	K1	R9	R9	R11	R3
87	R18	P2	P2	P2	R3	R1	R1	K2	R12
88	R4	V6	R9	R11	P2	R11	R11	R1	K1
89	R12	R17	R1	R24	R9	K1	K1	P1	R5
90	P1	R9	R11	P1	P1	R3	P1	R3	R30
91	K1	R11	P1	R6	R11	P1	R3	K1	R24
92	R6	R5	K1	K1	R5	R5	R5	R5	R18

Table D: CC rank matrix for 92 building form variants at 9 study locations, with global ranking per sum of location ranks. Yellow for top rankings, grey for bottom.

CC form ranking per location												
form code	LAG	DAK	RIY	ALE	ATH	BOL	LON	AAR	REY	rank sum	global rank	
B1	49	57	19	22	14	16	32	21	17	247	6	
B2	18	30	43	40	58	77	64	83	67	480	59	
B3	38	27	54	37	25	10	17	10	7	225	1	
B4	16	40	37	43	54	69	65	69	68	460	55	
B5	47	68	11	13	8	23	37	31	31	269	12	
B6	27	13	87	70	34	1	10	6	56	283	16	
B7	35	38	35	61	51	64	66	68	69	487	62	
B8	60	83	5	2	1	37	51	37	39	315	26	
B9	46	59	17	23	15	19	28	22	18	247	6	
B10	23	24	44	41	59	75	67	70	70	473	57	
B11	45	23	51	44	26	11	18	11	3	232	2	
B12	36	28	52	55	67	62	68	71	71	510	70	
B13	55	69	12	14	2	25	38	32	25	272	14	
B14	28	10	69	76	36	4	7	7	60	286	19	
B15	16	32	49	56	60	67	69	72	72	493	65	
B16	56	76	1	6	3	34	54	38	40	310	25	
B17	62	61	20	24	16	20	29	23	19	264	9	
B18	33	33	45	57	55	71	70	73	73	510	70	
B19	39	25	55	45	23	7	19	12	8	233	3	
B20	29	31	36	46	61	73	71	74	74	495	66	
B21	48	70	13	16	9	27	39	33	26	280	15	
B22	21	11	70	74	38	5	6	5	56	286	19	
B23	24	29	46	58	56	65	63	75	75	491	63	
B24	59	80	2	3	4	40	55	39	41	323	31	
B25	50	55	21	21	17	17	30	24	20	255	8	
B26	30	34	47	47	62	68	72	76	76	512	72	
B27	40	20	56	48	24	9	20	13	9	239	5	
B28	17	35	38	49	57	63	73	77	77	486	61	
B29	57	71	15	10	5	29	40	30	27	284	18	
B30	19	8	71	77	39	2	8	8	51	283	16	
B31	25	26	39	50	63	66	74	78	78	499	67	
B32	53	81	3	4	6	38	56	40	42	323	31	
B33	51	62	18	25	18	15	31	25	21	266	10	
B34	20	22	40	59	64	70	75	79	79	608	69	
B35	37	19	57	51	27	8	21	14	4	238	4	
B36	32	36	48	52	65	72	76	80	80	541	78	
B37	54	72	14	11	10	26	41	34	28	290	22	
B38	26	9	72	75	42	3	9	9	67	302	23	
B39	22	37	41	53	66	74	77	81	81	532	77	
B40	68	79	4	5	7	39	57	41	43	333	34	
R1	6	1	89	85	83	87	87	88	88	52	578	81
R2	79	77	9	16	11	44	42	43	38	359	39	
R3	4	65	78	31	87	90	91	90	86	622	84	
R4	88	54	50	68	30	48	15	44	5	402	45	
R5	1	92	82	1	92	92	92	92	89	633	86	
R6	92	14	85	91	69	55	2	48	66	522	74	
R7	5	2	66	80	84	83	79	63	22	504	68	
R8	76	76	7	12	19	43	43	46	32	363	38	
R9	3	90	88	84	89	86	86	84	61	671	88	
R10	85	53	32	62	40	31	16	49	10	378	41	
R11	2	91	90	88	91	88	88	95	83	707	90	
R12	89	12	83	86	79	28	4	55	87	523	75	
R13	9	15	81	79	72	22	25	26	11	340	36	
R14	67	74	8	9	20	35	34	42	33	322	30	
R15	8	84	75	71	77	60	61	52	36	624	76	
R16	81	46	33	38	43	18	14	35	12	320	29	
R17	7	89	78	89	80	78	80	64	62	593	83	
R18	87	5	80	81	78	6	3	46	92	478	58	
R19	31	16	66	64	41	13	23	19	13	286	19	
R20	63	73	10	17	12	45	33	27	29	309	24	
R21	41	67	53	26	31	41	52	47	34	392	42	
R22	75	41	42	65	32	47	11	3	2	318	28	
R23	43	86	31	19	28	50	60	50	58	425	47	
R24	82	4	79	89	68	51	1	1	91	466	56	
R25	44	18	63	54	29	12	22	15	14	271	13	
R26	62	75	6	7	21	42	53	28	30	324	33	
R27	61	66	22	18	22	32	49	36	35	341	37	
R28	68	47	24	27	48	21	26	4	1	266	10	
R29	65	82	16	8	13	48	59	51	59	399	43	
R30	77	6	73	78	81	14	12	2	90	433	49	
P1	90	44	91	90	90	91	90	89	85	760	92	
P2	12	87	87	87	88	85	85	85	37	663	87	
P3	10	64	74	72	82	58	44	53	24	461	60	
P4	69	60	59	60	36	49	27	16	23	399	43	
P5	73	63	25	20	33	36	35	17	15	317	27	
K1	91	3	92	92	86	89	89	91	88	721	91	
K2	83	17	84	83	85	84	84	87	82	689	89	
K3	42	43	68	66	75	79	62	65	60	560	79	
K4	34	62	58	63	62	61	58	61	53	492	64	
K5	64	42	34	29	50	59	50	62	54	444	54	
C1	74	51	26	39	44	53	45	55	45	433	49	
C2	71	48	27	30	49	57	38	57	46	421	46	
C3	66	49	28	32	45	56	46	59	47	428	48	
C4	72	50	29	33	46	52	47	60	48	437	62	
C5	70	45	30	34	47	54	48	58	49	435	51	
V1	80	56	23	35	37	33	24	29	16	333	34	
V2	11	58	64	42	70	78	81	64	44	512	72	
V3	84	21	61	73	53	30	13	20	6	361	40	
V4	13	85	62	36	71	80	82	66	65	660	79	
V5	86	7	77	82	76	24	5	18	63	438	53	
V6	14	88	60	28	73	82	83	67	84	579	82	
H1	78	39	65	67	74	81	78	82	64	628	85	